

Olefin Epoxidation catalysed by Manganese(III) Schiff Base Complexes : Evidence of Oxomanganese(IV) Formation

D. D. AGARWAL*, RAJEEV JAIN, RACHANA RASTOGI and VINITA AGARWAL
School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 5 May 1994, accepted 4 April 1995

Epoxidation of cyclohexene shows that ligands with N₄ system are better catalyst. Epoxide yield decreases with increase in catalyst concentration. Competitive epoxidation of cycloolefins using 0.001 mmol catalyst shows that breaking of olefin-catalyst complex is the rate-determining step, while 0.01 mmol catalyst suggests that formation of oxomanganese is the rate-determining step. *cis*-Stilbene gave a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-epoxides. Norbornene gave only *exo*-epoxide. Nonionic surfactant catalyses the norbornene epoxidation and pyridine addition improves the yield. Epr, ir and cyclic voltammetry support the formation of oxomanganese(IV) species as one of the oxidising species.

Synthetic metalloporphyrin complexes of iron, manganese, chromium and ruthenium etc. have been the focus of intense studies as models for the monooxygenase enzyme cytochrome P-450¹⁻⁴. The mechanism of manganese porphyrin catalysed reaction are not clear due to the different kinetic data obtained⁵. An oxomanganese(V) species has been suggested as possible oxidant using Mn(P)x/NaOCl system⁵. Mn(P)x/m-Cl perbenzoic acid system gave oxomanganese(IV) and -(V) as the two oxidising species². Here we report some Mn^{III} Schiff base complexes synthesised using a new route and the epoxidation catalysed by these complexes.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis, magnetic, conductance and ir spectral data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF Mn^{III} SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. no	Compd.	Analysis % :			Cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻² mol ⁻¹
		Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	
1.	[Mn(hyd Pn) NCS]	63.41 (63.22)	4.01 (4.02)	8.53 (8.48)	28.0
2.	[Mn(hyd Phen) NCS]	66.75 (65.96)	3.42 (3.50)	7.98 (7.92)	26.0
3.	[Mn(PcPn)(NCS) ₂] ⁺	51.74 (52.59)	4.39 (4.32)	19.23 (19.18)	78.6
4.	[Mn(PcPhen)(NCS) ₂] ⁺	57.28 (57.26)	3.51 (3.60)	17.58 (17.60)	84.2
5.	[Mn(Hapen) NCS]	56.15 (56.18)	4.43 (4.42)	10.34 (10.20)	23.8
6.	[Mn(Hap trien) NCS]	57.14 (57.04)	5.23 (5.21)	10.00 (10.00)	26.5
7.	[Mn(Hap Pn) NCS]	57.14 (57.00)	5.23 (5.18)	10.00 (9.79)	28.2
8.	[Mn(Hap Phen) NCS]	60.79 (60.72)	4.40 (4.34)	9.25 (9.12)	24.8

Sl. nos. 1, 2, 5, 7 : ν_{max} 1580–1595 (C=N), 2040–2050, 1250 cm⁻¹ (C=O)

Epoxidation of cyclohexene gave cyclohexene oxide along with cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone (Table 2). The results show that ligand having N₄ system are better catalyst compared to those having N₂O₂ system. In catalyst [Mn(PcPn)(NCS)₂]⁺ and [Mn(PcPhen)(NCS)₂]⁺, the two pyridyl groups probably reduces the electronegativity of oxomanganese oxygen making it more electrophilic and hence the oxomanganese bond⁷ is weakened thus oxygen can be transferred easily to alkene resulting in increased rate and yield of the epoxide.

The variation in catalyst concentration (Table 3) shows that at lower concentration better yield of epoxide is obtained. This shows that at higher concentration the oxomanganese responsible for epoxidation reacts with manganese(III) resulting in μ-oxodimer formation. Thus oxomanganese(V) is used up in unproductive side-reaction.

TABLE 2—EPOXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE USING Mn^{III} SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl no.*	Catalyst turnover no.	Epoxide mmol	Cyclohexenol mmol	Cyclohexenone mmol
1.	86	0.086	0.063	0.060
2.	48	0.048	0.658	0.291
3.	204	0.204	0.520	0.312
4.	329	0.329	0.628	0.061
5.	46	0.046	0.618	0.216
6.	96	0.096	0.424	0.087
7.	39	0.039	0.541	0.278
8.	31	0.031	0.364	0.031

*Corresponds to compounds as in Table 1.

Individual epoxidation of cyclo-olefins follows the order : cycloheptene (6.5) > norbornene (5.2) > cyclohexene (1.0)⁸. The competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefin follows the order : norbornene (4.70) > cyclohexene (1.0) > cycloheptene (0.40), but this order changes to norbornene (3.95) > cycloheptene (1.51) > cyclohexene (1.0)²²

when catalyst concentration was changed from 0.001 to 0.01 mmol. This observation can be explained by the fact that at 0.01 mmol catalyst concentration two reactions are competing (i) reaction of olefin to oxomanganese complex **2** to give epoxide, (ii) reaction of oxomanganese complex **2** with manganese and (iii) complex to give μ -oxodimer (**4**). Under such condition, the highly reactive alkene will react faster with oxomanganese complex while unreactive alkene will allow the formation of μ -oxodimer (**4**) thus giving low yield of epoxide. At 0.001 mmol catalyst concentration, the rate-determining step is shifted to the formation of **3** which breaks down to give epoxide. These observations help in clarifying the contradictory observations reported by other workers^{5,9}.

Epoxidation stereochemistry : *cis*-Hexene-2 gave *cis*-epoxide, and *trans*-hexene-2 gave *trans*-epoxide ($K_{cis}/K_{trans} = 3.0$). This shows that the steric factor due to the ligand plays a role in determining the relative reactivity of the olefins. *cis*-Stilbene gave a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-epoxide (*cis/trans* ratio = 2.75) along with deoxybenzoin and diphenylacetaldehyde. The addition of pyridine did not change the *cis/trans* ratio, a behaviour contrary to Mn(TPP)x/NaOCl system³. Norbornene on epoxidation gave only *exo*-norbornene oxide (a) along with small quantities of cyclohexene 4-carboxaldehyde (b) and norcamphor (c). The two latter products are obtained as a result of rearrangement of exoepoxide⁴ (a).

This observation is in contrast to that observed with manganese(III) porphyrin-catalysed epoxidations³. This suggests that it is the nature of the ligand that accounts for the product stereochemistry.

The effects of anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants micelles on norbornene epoxidation show that nonionic micelles catalyse the reaction giving high yield while anionic and cationic surfactants retard the yield. The addition of pyridine increased the yield of epoxide and rearrangement products. This shows that rearrangement accompanies epoxidation. Pyridine addition makes Mn-O bond weak and an easy transfer to the substrate⁷.

Epr studies : The epr spectra of freshly prepared solution of Mn(hyd Pn)NCS + PhIO in acetonitrile showed no signal but after few minutes it showed signals characteristics of a manganese(IV)¹⁰ complex. It showed that initially formed product was epr-silent but decomposed readily to give manganese(IV). The major feature of the epr spectrum is a strong signal at $G \approx 2$ and three broad and weak signals at low-field (1000–1500 G). It is known that nature and complexity of d^3 ion epr spectra in frozen solution depend on zero-field splitting parameters. When the axial parameter D is small ($2D \ll 0.31 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), the dominating signal lies at $g \approx 2$ attached by one or more weak signals at low field. Thus the spectra observed is that of high-spin $s = 3/2$ manganese(IV) derivative.

Ir spectra : A mixture of iodosylbenzene and Mn(hyd Pn)NCS solution after stirring for 5 min was filtered and subjected to ir analysis showing a new peak at 1040 cm^{-1} attributed to Mn^{IV}=O group¹¹.

Cyclic voltammetry : The cyclic voltammetry of Mn(hyd Pn)NCS showed both oxidation as well reduction waves. Anodic current at +0.68 V correspond to the oxidation Mn^{III} $\rightarrow$ Mn^{IV} which is again reduced to Mn^{III} at +0.42. This is a quasireversible oxidation couple. Quasireversible reduction behaviour $E_{pc} -0.38 \text{ V}$ and $E_{pa} -0.26 \text{ V}$, suggest a Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} couple. The value of i_{pc}/i_{pa} for Mn^{II}/Mn^{IV} couple was 1.71 and that for Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} couple¹² was 1.62. There was no evidence for Mn^V/Mn^{IV} couple. Coulometric data confirm the one-electron character of both the couples. The electrochemical oxidation of Mn(hyd Pn)NCS at +0.70 V showed an epr spectra similar to that observed with Mn(hyd Pn)NCS/PhIO system. This shows that oxomanganese(IV) is formed in the catalytic system under investigation.

Mechanism : The results suggest that oxomanganese(V) and -(IV) are formed in the system :

The absence of allylic oxidation product at high catalyst concentration and the pyridine addition, suggest that oxomanganese(v) largely gave epoxide while oxomanganese(IV) prefer proton abstraction leading to alcohol formation.

Epoxidation of stilbene and norbornene is explained by two O-C bond formation at different rate but simultaneously, similar to that observed using cytochrome P-450¹³. In

stilbene the intermediate formed find sufficient time to undergo rotation ¹³ and in norbornene the bond formation seems to be fairly rapid giving no room to bond rotation.

TABLE 3 EFFECT OF CATALYST CONCENTRATION ON EPOXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE

Sl. no.	Catalyst mmol	Catalyst turnover no.	Epoxyd. mmol	Cyclohexenol mmol	Cyclohexenone mmol
1	0.0005	100	0.190	0.266	0.076
2	0.001	86	0.086	0.063	0.060
3	0.003	49	0.040	0.041	0.060
4	0.01	10	0.010	Nil	Nil

*Corresponds to compound as in Table 1

Experimental

Epoxynorbornene, norcamphor and cyclohexene-4-carboxaldehyde (Aldrich) were used. *endo*-Epoxynorbornene was synthesised¹⁴. Stilbenes (*cis* and *trans*) were dissolved in hexane and chromatographed on a column of alumina. The solvent was removed and olefin stored at -20°. The other experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹⁴.

The CHN analyses of the complexes was recorded using a Carlo-Erba analyser. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured using a digital conductivity bridge having a dip type cell. Cyclic voltammetric studies were done using platinum as working electrode, Pt wire as auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode using a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system. Epr spectra were recorded on a Varian 109 CE-line X-band spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar for measurement at 77 K; spectra were calculated with the help of DPPH (g = 2.0037).

TABLE 4-EFFECT OF ADDITIVES ON EPOXIDATION OF NORBORNENE

Sl no	Additive	Norbornene oxide mmol	Other products mmol
1	No additive	0.450	0.026
2	S L S	0.203	0.035
3	Triton X-100	1.37	Nil
4	CTABr	0.213	Nil
5	Pyridine	1.68	1.45
6	Benzene	0.382	Nil

*Corresponds to compound as in Table 1

Synthesis of the complexes. The manganese(III) complexes were synthesised using ligands, viz. bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)propylenediamine (H₂HydPn), bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)-*o*-phenylenediamine (H₂hyd-Phen), bis(pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde)propylenediamine (PcPn), bis(pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde)-*o*-phenylenediamine (PcPhen), bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)methylenediamine (H₂hapen), bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)ethylenediamine (H₂hap trien), bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-

propylenediamine (H₂hap pn) and bis(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-*o*-phenylenediamine (H₂hap phen) (0.001 mol) acetoneitrile and reacting the ligand with Mn(acac)₃ NCS (0.001 mol) in hot acetonitrile solution. The contents were stirred and refluxing for 30 min gave shining crystals, which were separated, after cooling, washed with ether and dried.

Epoxidation of cyclohexene: Epoxidation of cyclohexene (2.5 mmol) using various manganese Schiff base catalyst (0.001 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 ml) was carried out using iodossylbenzene (0.50 mmol) as oxidant under N₂-atmosphere. The contents were stirred at room temperature (30°). Then the contents were filtered and the products analysed by GC using XE-60 column at 120°.

Effect of catalyst concentration: The effect of change in catalyst concentration on the epoxidation of cyclohexene was studied taking Mn(hyd Pn)NCS concentrations as 0.0005, 0.001, 0.002 and 0.01 mmol.

Competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins: The competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins, viz. cyclohexene, cycloheptene and norbornene was studied taking cyclic olefin (2.5 mmol), catalyst Mn(hyd Pn)NCS (0.001 mmol) and iodossylbenzene (1.0 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 ml). The products were analysed using XE-60 column. The competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins was also studied at 0.01 mmol concentration of the catalyst.

Effect of pyridine, sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) and Triton X-100 on the epoxidation of norbornene (2.5 mmol) was studied by stirring a mixture of catalyst (0.001 mmol), additive (50 mg), iodossylbenzene (0.50 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 ml) for 1 h and analysed.

The epoxidation of *cis*-, *trans*-hexene-2, and *cis*-, *trans*-stilbene was studied using the olefin (2.5 mmol), catalyst Mn(hyd Pn)NCS (0.001 mmol) and iodossylbenzene (0.50 mmol).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. Chakravorty, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, for providing electrochemical and epr facilities and to Dr. Gautam Lahuri for technical help. The financial assistance from U G C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. K. A. JORGENSEN, *Chem Rev.*, 1989, 89, 431, R.H. HOIM, *Chem Rev.*, 1987, 87, 1401, J. M. GARRISON and T. C. BRUCE, *J Am Chem Soc.* 1989, 111, 191, W. NAM and J. S. V. MENZIE, *New J Chem.*, 1989, 13, 677, J. T. GROVES, I. E. NEMO and R. S. MYERS, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1979, 101, 1032, J. I. GROVES and I. E. NEMO, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1983, 105, 5786, J. R. LINDSAY SMITH and P. R. SEPAHL, *J Chem Soc., Perkin Trans 2*, 1982, 1009, D. MANSUY, J. LUCI SIRE, M. FORTICAVI and M. MOMENTEAU, *Bio-chem Biophys Res Commun.*, 1984, 119, 319, I. G. FRAWLOR, J. C. MARSTERS, T. NAKANO and B. F. DUNLOP, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1985, 107, 5537, K. SRINIVASAN and J. K. KOCH, *Inorg Chem.* 1984, 24, 4671, D. D. AGARWAL, *J Mol Catal.*, 1988, 44, 65, J. T. GROVES

AGARWAL, JAIN, RASTOGI & AGARWAL : OLEFIN EPOXIDATION CATALYSED BY MANGANESE(III) SCHIFF BASE *etc.*

- and Y. WATANABE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 785
- J. T. GROVES and M. K. STERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 3812.
 - B. MEUNIER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1986, 578.
 - T. G. TRAYLOR and A. R. MIKSZTAL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 7443.
 - R. J. M. NOLTE, J. A. S. REZENBERG and R. SCHIURMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 2751.
 - O. BARTOLINI and B. MEUNIER, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 1364.
 - K. A. JORGENSEN and J. SWAUSTROM, *Acta Chem. Scand.* 1988, **43**, 822.
 - E. L. ELIEL, "Stereochemistry of Carbon Compounds", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
 - J. P. COLLMAN, J. I. BRAUMAN, B. MEUNIER, S. A. RAYBUCK and T. KODADAK, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1984, **81**, 3245
 - S. PAL, P. GHOSH and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 3704; M. SCHAPPACHER and R. WEISS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 1190; D. P. KESSISSOGLU, W. M. BUTLER and V. L. PECORARO, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 1253.
 - M. TIRANT and T. D. SMITH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **121**, 5.
 - W. M. COLEMAN, R. R. GOCHRING, L. T. TAYLOR, J. G. MASON and R. K. BOGESS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 2311.
 - R. P. HANZLIK and G. O. SHEARER, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1978, **27**, 1441.
 - D. D. AGARWAL, R. JAIN, R.P. BHATNAGAR and S. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1990, 989; *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1990, **59**, 385.

